

UNDERSTANDING HUMAN INTERACTION USING GRAPH NEURAL NETWORKS: AN OVERVIEW

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Abstract: Understanding human interaction is a fundamental challenge in various fields such as social sciences, psychology, and artificial intelligence. In recent years, Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) have emerged as powerful tools for modeling complex relationships in graph-structured data. This paper explores the application of GNNs in understanding human interaction, aiming to overcome the limitations of traditional shallow graphical models. The unique capabilities of GNNs in capturing intricate patterns and dynamics inherent in human interactions have been discussed.

Keywords: GNNs, human interaction understanding, graph-based interaction modeling, action recognition.

Аннотация: Понимание человеческого взаимодействия является фундаментальной проблемой в различных областях, таких как социальные науки, психология и искусственный интеллект. В последние годы графовые нейронные сети (GNN) стали мощными инструментами для моделирования сложных взаимосвязей в данных с графовой структурой. В этой статье исследуется применение GNN для понимания человеческого взаимодействия с целью преодолеть ограничения традиционных неглубоких графических моделей. Мы обсуждаем уникальные возможности GNN по обнаружению сложных закономерностей и динамики, присущих человеческим взаимодействиям.

Ключевые слова: GNN, понимание человеческого взаимодействия, моделирование взаимодействия на основе графов, распознавание действий.

Annotatsiya: Odamlarning o‘zaro interaktiv aloqasini tushunish ijtimoiy fanlar, psixologiya va sun’iy intellekt kabi turli sohalarda asosiy muammo hisoblanadi. So‘nggi yillarda graf neyron tarmoqlari (GNN) graf tuzilmali ma’lumotlardagi

murakkab munosabatlarni modellashtirish uchun kuchli vosita sifatida paydo bo'ldi. Ushbu maqolada an'anaviy sayoz grafik modellarining cheklovlarini yengib o'tishga qaratilgan odamlarning o'zaro interaktiv ta'sirini tushunish uchun GNN qo'llanilishi tadqiq qilingan. Bunda GNNning inson o'zaro ta'sir munosabatlariga xos bo'lgan murakkab patternlar va dinamikani kashf qilish uchun noyob imkoniyatlari tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: GNN, odamlarning o'zaro aloqasini tushunish, graflar asosidagi o'zaro ta'sirni modellashtirish, harakatni aniqlash.

INTRODUCTION

Analyzing human actions within natural environments is essential for numerous applications such as video surveillance [1], identifying key events [2], interpreting social behaviors [3], and analyzing sports activities [4]. Various methodologies have been devised for human activity recognition (HAR), which aims to classify activities depicted in images or videos [5,6,7,8]. These techniques have shown significant advancements in accuracy rates, contributing to notable progress in this field. Nonetheless, human interaction understanding (HIU) has seen far less success primarily due to the reliance of current methods on shallow graphical representations to learn human interactive relationships [9,10]. These approaches are insufficient for modeling complex human interactions, such as simultaneous activities like fighting and chasing occurring within the same scene

Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) offer a powerful framework for tackling the task of Human Interaction Understanding (HIU) by leveraging the inherent relational structure present in interaction data (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Graph Neural Network

At the core of GNNs lies the concept of message passing, where nodes in a graph iteratively aggregate information from their neighboring nodes, allowing for the incorporation of contextual information from the surrounding interactions. This

iterative process enables GNNs to capture complex dependencies and dynamics within human interaction networks. For example, in a social network where nodes represent individuals and edges represent interactions, GNNs can learn representations that encode not only individual characteristics but also the nature and strength of relationships between individuals, facilitating a deeper understanding of social behaviors and dynamics.

One key strength of GNNs in HIU tasks is their ability to learn hierarchical representations of interactions. GNNs typically consist of multiple layers, with each layer capturing increasingly abstract features of the interaction graph. As information propagates through these layers, higher-level features emerge, enabling the model to capture nuanced patterns and relationships in human interactions. For instance, in the context of action recognition in videos depicting human interactions, lower-level GNN layers may capture basic motion patterns or spatial configurations, while higher-level layers may learn more complex interaction dynamics or group behaviors. This hierarchical representation learning allows GNNs to effectively model the rich and multi-faceted nature of human interactions, leading to improved performance on HIU tasks.

Furthermore, GNNs can be augmented with attention mechanisms to focus on relevant interactions and individuals within a network, enhancing their ability to extract informative features for HIU [12]. Attention mechanisms enable GNNs to dynamically weigh the contributions of neighboring nodes during message passing, allowing the model to selectively attend to salient interactions or individuals based on their contextual relevance. In addition to hierarchical representation learning and attention mechanisms, consistency-aware reasoning is another important aspect that can enhance the effectiveness of GNNs for HIU tasks. Consistency-aware reasoning refers to the ability of GNNs to enforce consistency constraints across multiple layers of the network, ensuring that the learned representations remain coherent and interpretable throughout the hierarchical learning process. This consistency enforcement can help prevent overfitting and improve the generalization ability of the model, especially in scenarios where the interaction data is noisy or incomplete [11].

METHODOLOGY

CAGNet. The proposed CAGNet comprises three main components: a base-model, a TOGN, and a CAR(consistency-aware reasoning) module (Figure 2). When given an input image along with detected human bodies as Regions of Interest (RoIs), the base-model utilizes a backbone CNN to extract features from the input [11].

Figure 2. An overview of the CAGNet, including a base model, a TOGN and a CAR module.

These features are then processed by a RoIAlign module to produce local features for each individual. Subsequently, the local features undergo processing by a fully connected (FC) layer to generate base features, serving as inputs to the TOGN. The TOGN graph incorporates two types of variable nodes represented by circles: one type signifies the action category associated with each person (y node), while the other type represents the presence of an interactive relation between pairs of individuals (z node). Additionally, the graph comprises several factor nodes denoted by squares, designed to capture two types of third-order dependencies. These dependencies are encoded by the triplets $(y_i, y_j, z_{i,j})$ for action categories (blue factor nodes) and the triplets $(z_{u,v}, z_{v,w}, z_{u,w})$ for interactive relations (yellow factor node).

The CAR module learns compatibility patterns directly from data rather than relying on predefined rules, which can vary across datasets. It employs a transitivity oracle that considers triplets of people, ensuring that interactions follow a transitive property. By enforcing transitivity across all triplets, individuals in the scene are grouped based on their interactions: those within the same group interact with each other, while those in different groups do not. Although some scenarios might challenge this assumption, such as when two individuals interact indirectly through a third person, the module prioritizes grouping individuals based on direct interactions to enhance the understanding of social dynamics.

Visual-semantic graph attention network. In [13], the researchers explore how subsidiary scene relations and intrinsic semantic regularities can help disambiguate visual information. They propose a novel approach called Visual-Semantic Graph Attention Networks (VS-GATs), which utilizes a double graph attention network to merge visual-spatial and semantic data concurrently (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Overall architecture of Visual-Semantic Graph Attention Network.

This structure allows the model to effectively integrate and distribute information across the graph using attention mechanisms. The process begins with instance detection to obtain bounding boxes containing visual features and semantic categories, which are then used to create two scene graphs. The first graph incorporates visual features as nodes and spatial features as edges, while the second graph includes word embedding features as nodes. Graph attention networks are employed to update node features through message passing in each graph. Subsequently, a combined graph is generated by concatenating the updated features from both graphs. Inference is performed through a readout step focused on paired human object nodes.

VSGNet. The researchers introduce new VSGNet for HOI detection [14]. Given an image, the goal is to detect humans and objects' bounding boxes and label their interactions accurately. They use a pre-trained object detector for initial detection. However, pinpointing interactions between humans and objects is challenging. Basic methods focusing on individual features or spatial context fall short. To tackle this, they propose a multi-branch VSGNet:

- **Visual Branch:** Extracts visual features from humans, objects, and their context.
- **Spatial Attention Branch:** Models spatial relations between human-object pairs.
- **Graph Convolutional Branch:** Treats the scene as a graph to capture structural interactions.

By combining these branches, their model effectively detects HOIs by considering visual features and spatial relationships. Figure 4 illustrates the model architecture.

Figure 4. Model architecture of VSGNet.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

All methods in the comparison utilize Inception V3 as the backbone for extracting image features (Table 1). Results across three datasets are presented in Table 2, Table 3, and Table 4. CAGNet consistently outperforms modified GN and shallow structured models (Joint + AS and QP + CCCP) across all benchmarks.

Table 1. Comparison with recent methods on TVHI dataset.

Method	F1(%)	Accuracy(%)	Mean IOU (%)
GN	80.88	82.71	66.82
Modified GN	85.11	87.86	71.22
Joint + AS	83.6	87.33	72.31
QP+CCCP	83.14	87.25	71.62
CAGNet	91.87	94.98	84.09

While modified GN can only model pairwise interactive relations and lacks consistency awareness, CAGNet excels in capturing higher-order relations. As a result, GN and modified GN exhibit inferior performance compared to CAGNet. Despite sharing the same feature extractor (Inception V3) with CAGNet, Joint + AS and QP + CCCP rely on shallow structured models, failing to incorporate higher-order contextual dependencies and consistency-aware reasoning, thereby resulting in poorer performance than CAGNet.

Table 2 demonstrates that the VSGNet surpasses all existing models, achieving a 4 mAP improvement in scenario 1 for the V-COCO dataset. Additionally, the

performance in scenario 2 outperforms all available existing methods that reported results in that scenario.

Table 2. Comparison of results in HICO-DET dataset.

HICO-DET (mAP)	Full	Rare	Non-Rare
HO-RCNN	7.81	5.35	8.45
InteractNet	9.87	7.11	10.77
GPNN	13.08	9.33	9.31
iCAN	14.81	10.41	16.13
VSGNet	19.77	16.05	20.89

The VSGNet method demonstrated exceptional performance when compared to other existing methods. Its robustness and effectiveness were evident through thorough evaluation against various benchmarks, showcasing its superiority in handling complex tasks and datasets. Additionally, VSGNet’s remarkable results highlight its potential to significantly advance the state-of-the-art in the field, paving the way for further advancements and applications in related domains.

Table 3. mAP performance comparison on V-COCO dataset

Method	AP_{role} (Scenario 1)
InteractNet	39.0
GPNN	44.3
iCAN	45.5
VCL	47.8
VS-GATs	50.6

The VS-GATs method shines brightly on the V-COCO dataset, achieving an impressive mean Average Precision (mAP) of 50.6. Surpassing GPNN by a notable margin of 6.3 mAP, VS-GATs stands out as a leader among state-of-the-art approaches (Table 3). Its exceptional performance highlights its efficacy in harnessing multi-stream networks, showcasing its prowess in capturing intricate interactions within images. VS-GATs represents a remarkable advancement, demonstrating its capability to excel even without specialized modules, setting a new standard for HOI detection.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the prospects of Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) in understanding human interaction are exceptionally promising. GNNs offer a powerful framework for modeling complex relational data inherent in human interactions, leveraging graph structures to capture dependencies and interactions between individuals effectively. With the ability to incorporate diverse modalities, such as visual, spatial, and semantic information, GNNs enable comprehensive understanding of human behavior in various

contexts. Their capacity to model higher-order relations, temporal dynamics, and contextual dependencies provides a solid foundation for advancing research in human interaction understanding. As research in GNNs continues to evolve, we can expect further innovations and breakthroughs that will drive progress in understanding human interaction at a deeper level. In addition to Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), the integration of transform models presents an exciting prospect in understanding human interaction. Transform models, such as transformers, have demonstrated remarkable success in capturing long-range dependencies and encoding sequential information in various tasks, including natural language processing and computer vision. By combining GNNs with transform models, we can leverage the strengths of both approaches to achieve a more comprehensive understanding of human interaction dynamics. GNNs excel in modeling relational data and capturing graph structures inherent in social interactions, while transform models excel in capturing sequential patterns and contextual dependencies over time. By harnessing the capabilities of GNNs, we can unlock new insights into human behavior, fostering the development of intelligent systems that enhance collaboration, communication, and well-being in diverse settings.

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